

Minimal Metadata

A session of the Open Source Science Data Repositories Workshop 2025 held in Huntsville, AL on Aug 25-27, 2025.

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The Minimal Metadata session was one of five parts of the round robin session of the Open Source Science Data Repositories Workshop 2025. It was included in the workshop to provide a short feedback time to each of five rotating groups on metadata fields and their proposed associated requirement levels for mission and research data. The metadata field selections and the proposed requirement levels were developed based on outputs of the Minimal Metadata portion of the “Defining Minimum FAIR Compliance across NASA” session at the previous year’s workshop (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14225088>). In the session, each rotating group was given a short introduction to the material, including the definitions for mission and research data from SPD-41a¹, and instructed to vote on each field if they had an objection to the proposed associated requirement level. Comments were invited for any explanations desired and for additional metadata fields to be added. In-person attendees did not cast any votes but instead contributed through discussion and comments (see Appendix). Virtual attendees did cast votes but in most cases these were for the proposed associated requirement level, not objections (see Appendix).

The table below presents the voting results on the metadata fields presented, where the final requirement level reflects the lowest requirement level requested for each field per category, whether by votes or comments. If no votes were cast for a given metadata field and no related comments were given, the proposed associated requirement level is considered accepted. It is a SMD best practice to use DataCite to create DOIs for all SMD-funded data products, which results in the metadata fields designated as mandatory by DataCite being also mandatory for the SMD data repository community. Thus, those metadata fields are excluded from the table since changes to DataCite’s requirements are out of scope. The remaining metadata fields are presented in column 1, with the final associated requirement level for each metadata field for mission data and research data shown in columns 2 and 3 respectively.

Metadata Field	Mission Req. Level*	Research Req. Level*
Description	R	R
Subject/Keyword	O	O
License (SPDX link)	R	R
Access Constraints (e.g., isAccessibleForFree)	R	R
NASA SMD Science Division(s)	O	O

¹ <https://science.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/smd-information-policy-spd-41a.pdf>

Version	O	R
Data Format	O	R
Funding Agency(ies)	O	O
Related Instrument (collected by)	O	O
Originating software	O	O
Originating data	O	O
Reference publication	O	R
OSDMP link	R	R
ORCID for at all NASA authors	O	O
Affiliations for all NASA authors	O	M
Publisher ROR	O	R**
Data Processing Level / Transparency Grade	O	O
Use Constraints	R	O
Spatial Bounds Coordinates	O	O
Spatial Bounds	O	O
Coordinate system	R	O
Link to documentation	O	R
Funding Award Number	O	R
Other creator ORCIDs	O	O
RORs for creator and contributor affiliations	O	O
Data Volume	O	O
Related Mission	R	N/A

*M = Mandatory, R = Recommended, O = Optional

**Requirement level downgraded from Mandatory based on feasibility (see text).

Objections to the requirement levels of several metadata fields were based on the lack of relevance or feasibility across all NASA SMD science areas of research, such as spatial bounds for biological sciences and space physics. The Publisher ROR field was voted to be mandatory for research data, but was downgraded to recommended since some generalist repositories do not have an ROR (e.g., Zenodo). Related Mission was not voted on for research data and is also not relevant for all types of research data (e.g., simulated data), so the field should be considered optional. A few additional metadata fields were suggested in the comments but were not voted on, including variable name, variable type, data collection year, temporal range, contact info, funding program, version date, wavelength bounds, spatial resolution, temporal

resolution, related sample ISGN, and algorithm theoretical basic document identifier. By default, these fields are considered optional across the SMD data repositories.

In summary, no metadata fields beyond those required by DataCite were voted to be mandatory for mission data. The only metadata field voted to be mandatory for research data is the **Affiliations** field for all NASA authors, which needs confirmation by the SMD data repository community. All other fields in both categories were voted as either recommended or optional. Moving forward, the requirement level of all non-mandatory metadata fields for mission and research data must be determined by the NASA SMD Divisions for the data funded by their Division, where the Division-recommended requirement level is ideally not lower than that presented here.

The next steps for defining the minimal metadata requirements for NASA SMD is to

- Check with the NASA SMD data repository community for any objections against the Affiliations field for all NASA authors for research data being mandatory, and if so, what requirement level is preferred.
- If any objections are received, downgrade the associated requirement level for the Affiliations field for all NASA authors to the lowest requirement level requested.
- Document the list above with any needed change to the indicated field as the final SMD-level guidance on metadata requirements for mission and research data for the SMD data repository community.
- Encourage each Division to develop and publicize Division-wide requirement levels for individual metadata fields separately for mission and research data, prioritizing fields supported by or mapped to DataCite to build on the existing SMD-wide best practice of using DataCite to create DOIs for datasets.

Appendix

This appendix consists of the pictures of the physical poster used to collect feedback during the session (Figures 1 and 2) and screenshots of the virtual Miro board used to collect feedback from virtual attendees. The link to the Miro board is https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVJXJu0qQ=. The author gives credit to an unnamed conference staff member who took the pictures of the physical poster.

		TITLE Publisher (Repository) Publication Year Landing Page URL (with access) Description Subject/ Keyword License (SPDX link) Access Constraints (e.g., isAccessibleForFree) NASA SMD Science Division(s) Resource Type (e.g., dataset, software, etc) Version Data Format (select all that apply) Funding Agency(ies) Related Instrument (collected by)
<p>CONTACT INFO (SEE WEBSITE) (ASK AND WEB PAGE OR ENLIGHTENED WEB PAGE HAS EMAIL INFO FOR QUESTIONS / DISCUSSIONS)</p> <p>SMD SCIENCE DIVISION CHANGES NEXT TIME ITS PROBABLY NOT BEING USEFUL</p>		
Comments	Vote	Mission Metadata
		Originating software (at least one software used to produce the data, ideally a DOI) Originating data (a dataset used to produce this one, typically a lower processing level, ideally a DOI) Reference publication (the publication the data provider wants others to cite in addition to the dataset, ideally a DOI). OSDMP link (ideally a DOI) ORCID for all NASA authors Affiliations for all NASA authors Data Processing Level Use Constraints (what to use or not use this for) Spatial Bounds Coordinates Spatial Bounds Coordinate system
		Instrument PID Funding Award # Spatial and temporal resolution (cadence) Long existing data formats already have minimum metadata requirements
Comments	Vote	Mission Metadata
		Link to documentation (or included with submission) Funding Award Number Other creator ORCIDs RORs for creator and contributor affiliations Data Volume Related Mission (could be linked through the instrument record)
		platform + instrument IDs (?)
		Optional Metadata
		ATBD refs. Algorithm Theoretical Basis Doc. For Earth FROM A 100 JERS RECEIVED, FUNDING AWARDS AT SPAN NOT BE OPTIMAL (WATER) WHERE IS THE ROSES SOLICITATION #? I CAN SEE USING THAT FOR STORAGE/DIVISION METADATA

Figure 1: Screenshot of the physical poster used to collect feedback.

Mandatory	License (SPDX link) Access Constraints (e.g., isAccessibleForFree) NASA SMD Science Division(s) Resource Type (e.g., dataset, software, etc) Version Data Format (select all that apply) Funding Agency(ies) Data Volume (category choice, e.g., <200 GB, 200 GB to 20 TB, >20 TB)		
Recommended Metadata	Research Metadata Originating software (at least one software used to produce the data, ideally a DOI) Originating data (a dataset used to produce this one, typically a mission dataset, ideally a DOI) Reference publication (the publication the data provider wants others to cite in addition to the dataset, ideally a DOI). OSDMP link (ideally a DOI) ORCID for all NASA authors Affiliations for all NASA authors High Level Publisher ROR Data Transparency Grade (e.g., https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1464187)	DATA FORMAT NOT NECESSARY AS MANDATORY	Comments Sample PID IGSIV Experimental/Sample Table (Reference info) Subarray n Sen Instrument PID (Facility boundaries)
Optional Metadata	Research Metadata Link to documentation (or included with submission) Funding Award Number Other creator ORCIDs RORs for creator and contributor affiliations Use Constraints Spatial Bounds Coordinates Spatial Bounds Related Instrument (collected by) Coordinate System	Vote Funding Award shall be record	Comments Temporal Coverage For each instrument... Temporal + spatial coverage + location + coordinate system

Figure 2: Screenshot of the physical poster used to collect feedback.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the Miro board, mandatory mission data metadata section.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the Miro board, mandatory research data metadata section.

Comments	Vote	Mission Metadata	Recommended Metadata
		Originating software (at least one software used to produce the data, ideally a DOI)	
		Originating data (a dataset used to produce this one, typically a lower processing level, ideally a DOI)	
		Reference publication (the publication the data provider wants others to cite in addition to the dataset, ideally a DOI).	
		OSDMP link (ideally a DOI)	
		ORCID for all NASA authors	
		Affiliations for all NASA authors	
		Publisher ROR	
		Data Processing Level	
		Use Constraints (what to use or not use this for)	
		Spatial Bounds Coordinates	
		Spatial Bounds	
		Coordinate system	

what about wavelength bounds / time bounds?

How would this work for spacecraft missions? There's no way commercial partners would share something like flight path with us to make public

Heliophysics generally doesn't track software, only sometimes in the dataset metadata

like data volume, spatial bounds are also variable

spatial bounds aren't meaningful for space physics

Do we really want to offer bespoke dataset use constraints? Couldn't we have repository-wide data use agreements?

Spatial bounds are for individual products not the aggregate in most cases

Figure 5: Screenshot of the Miro board, recommended mission data metadata section.

	Research Metadata	Vote	Comments
Recommended Metadata	Originating software (at least one software used to produce the data, ideally a DOI)		
	Originating data (a dataset used to produce this one, typically a mission dataset, ideally a DOI)		
	Reference publication (the publication the data provider wants others to cite in addition to the dataset, ideally a DOI).		
	OSDMP link (ideally a DOI)		
	ORCID for all NASA authors		
	Affiliations for all NASA authors		
	Publisher ROR		
	Data Transparency Grade (e.g., https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14641876)		

more modern science data formats (SD 18115) have lineage info in files that is likely a better place to include "originating data" info. There are cases where several data products go into the generation of a data product and trying to manage this metadata in a way that is useful/hardly manageable

Research Area?

Figure 6: Screenshot of the Miro board, recommended research data metadata section.

Comments	Vote	Mission Metadata	
<p>Funding award number might be useful for research (e.g. ROSES) but isn't useful for missions.</p> <p>Funding award number should not be optional</p> <p>what is funding award # for non-NASA or non-SMD missions? -></p> <p>Funding award number should not be optional</p> <p>SPDF does not have a way to get funding info for many of our datasets, only current NASA Missions</p> <p>Related mission? What is useful is related data products.</p> <p>Data volume is not static if the dataset is not static.</p>		Link to documentation (or included with submission)	Optional Metadata
		Funding Award Number	
		Other creator ORCIDiDs	
		RORs for creator and contributor affiliations	
		Data Volume	
		Related Mission (could be linked through the instrument record)	

Figure 7: Screenshot of the Miro board, optional mission data metadata section.

	Research Metadata	Vote	Comments
Optional Metadata	Link to documentation (or included with submission)		<p>What does use constr</p> <p>related research or investigation</p>
	Funding Award Number		
	Other creator ORCIDiDs		
	RORs for creator and contributor affiliations		
	Use Constraints		
	Spatial Bounds Coordinates		
	Spatial Bounds		
	Related Instrument (collected by)		
	Coordinate System		

Figure 8: Screenshot of the Miro board, optional research data metadata section.